

DUAL TRAINING FOR MICE PERSONNEL IN UZBEKISTAN THROUGH PARENTAL ENGAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT. *The article substantiates the need for social support mechanisms within dual education to train personnel for Uzbekistan's business tourism sector (MICE). Against the backdrop of accelerated industry development, evidenced by growing potential revenues and expanding infrastructure, a persistent workforce risk remains, driven by a gap between educational trajectories and the actual labor regimes in hospitality. Based on an analysis of the regulatory framework for dual education, secondary statistical materials, and international research findings on staff turnover and the influence of family support on educational decisions, a parental engagement program is proposed to accompany students' professional trajectories. The program aims to increase families' awareness of occupation-specific realities, support students' learning and professional discipline, and reduce the likelihood of premature withdrawal from dual education and early exit from the workplace. A monitoring indicator system is developed to support piloting the program in partner MICE organizations.*

Keywords: *dual education, MICE tourism, staff turnover, parental education, professional motivation, staff retention, Uzbekistan, social support for learning.*

ANNOTATSIYA. *Maqolada O'zbekistonda biznes turizmi sektori MICE uchun kadrlar tayyorlashda dual ta'limni ijtimoiy jihatdan qo'llab quvvatlash zarurati asoslab beriladi. Tarmoqning jadal rivojlanishi, potensial daromadlarning o'sishi va infratuzilmaning kengayishi bilan tavsiflanuvchi sharoitda, mehmondo'stlik sohasidagi real mehnat rejimlari hamda ta'lim trayektoriyalari o'rtasidagi nomutanosiblik bilan bog'liq kadrlar xavfi saqlanib qolmoqda. Dual ta'limning me'yoriy huquqiy bazasi, ikkilamchi statistik materiallar hamda xodimlar qo'nimsizligi va oilaviy qo'llab quvvatlashning ta'limiy qarorlarga ta'siri bo'yicha xorijiy tadqiqotlar natijalari tahlili asosida talabalarning professional trayektoriyasini kuzatib borishda ota onalarni jalb etish dasturi taklif etiladi. Dastur kasbning o'ziga xos jihatlari haqida oilalarning xabardorligini oshirishga, talabalarning o'quv va kasbiy intizomini qo'llab quvvatlashga, shuningdek, dual ta'limdan muddatidan oldin chiqib ketish hamda ish joyini erta tark etish ehtimolini kamaytirishga yo'naltirilgan. Hamkor MICE tashkilotlarida dasturni pilot sinovdan o'tkazish uchun qo'llash mumkin bo'lgan monitoring ko'rsatkichlari tizimi shakllantirildi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *dual ta'lim, MICE turizmi, kadrlar qo'nimsizligi, ota onalar ma'rifati, professional motivatsiya, xodimlarni ushlab qolish, O'zbekiston, ta'limni ijtimoiy qo'llab quvvatlash.*

АННОТАЦИЯ. *В статье обосновывается необходимость социального сопровождения дуального обучения для подготовки кадров в секторе делового туризма (MICE) Узбекистана. На фоне ускоренного развития отрасли, фиксируемого ростом потенциальных доходов и расширением инфраструктуры, сохраняется кадровый риск, обусловленный разрывом между образовательными траекториями и реальными*

режимами труда в гостеприимстве. На основе анализа нормативной базы дуального образования, вторичных статистических материалов и результатов зарубежных исследований о текучести персонала и влиянии семейной поддержки на образовательные решения предложена программа вовлечения родителей в сопровождение профессиональной траектории студентов. Программа ориентирована на повышение информированности семей о специфике профессии, поддержание учебной и профессиональной дисциплины студентов, а также на снижение вероятности досрочного выхода из дуального обучения и раннего ухода с рабочего места. Сформирована система показателей мониторинга, применимая для пилотирования программы в партнёрских MICE-организациях.

Ключевые слова: *дуальное образование, MICE-туризм, кадровая текучесть, родительское просвещение, профессиональная мотивация, удержание персонала, Узбекистан, социальное сопровождение обучения*

Introduction

Uzbekistan’s reorientation toward the development of business tourism implies not only capital-intensive infrastructure solutions but also a sustainable workforce training system capable of operating under high variability in event demand, project-based employment, and heightened requirements for service standards. According to industry studies, the MICE segment demonstrates long-term growth, including a forecast increase in revenues from USD 961.1 million in 2019 to USD 1.78 billion by 2030 at an average annual rate of 6.1% [1]. The expansion of the hotel base, including the commissioning of new accommodation facilities, intensifies the need for qualified personnel able to work at the intersection of service delivery, logistics, and communication [2].

In response to workforce demand, the state has initiated the institutionalization of dual education within the vocational education system. The regulatory impulse is set by a range of strategic-level documents [3], while the basic organizational model is закреплена by Resolution No. 163 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 29, 2021, which provides for a combination of training in an educational organization and work at an enterprise, with at least two days per week in classroom learning and the remaining time at the workplace [4]. Important regulatory changes related to improving workforce training in tourism, including the establishment of the Silk Road International University of Tourism, are reflected in a number of presidential resolutions and decrees [5-7]. As a result, the scale of tourism-related training has increased substantially, leading to a larger number of students, host organizations, and mentors.

However, the formal linkage “educational institution-employer” does not remove the risk of early exit from the profession that is typical for hospitality. Labor market evidence in the sector points to structural constraints, including skill mismatches and unmet employer expectations. In the Asian Development Bank’s sector assessment, only 21% of companies characterize graduates’ training as relevant to labor market demand, whereas 32% report complete mismatch [8]. An additional contextual factor is the age structure of the labor market. In Uzbekistan, 60% of the population is youth under the age of 30 [9]. The size of this age cohort increases sensitivity to the quality of the first job and the stability of professional choice.

The problem of staff turnover in hospitality is considered in international literature as a key driver of service quality decline and rising transactional costs of recruitment. Empirical estimates for the United States indicate annual turnover at the level of 70-80%, accompanied by

costs of USD 4,700 to replace each departing employee [10]. Comparative, cross-industry materials based on BLS data confirm elevated turnover in “leisure and hospitality” at 20.7%, compared with an average of 3.3% across all industries and a threshold of up to 10% that Gallup considers healthy [11]. For Uzbekistan, where the dual model is at an early stage of adaptation, it is important to consider not only production and organizational factors but also social mechanisms that support professional choice. In an interview on transferring German experience, it is emphasized that systematic inclusion of the family in dual education has not yet been established, and cultural attitudes may reduce the perceived value of vocational education [12].

International studies demonstrate a robust link between family support and educational persistence. Based on evidence from Scandinavian research by E. Schmid and V. Garrels, parental support often becomes a critical factor for retaining vulnerable learner groups within education and for developing career confidence [13]. A. Oomen’s analysis of parental education programs across countries shows that two-generation and “parents-as-mentors” models can improve educational outcomes, including higher completion of training modules and reduced family anxiety during transitions [14]. Complementing this context, research by S. Xiaoli, W. Fengxia, and L. Mengyao on the influence of family background on career choice indicates that parents’ educational level and professional trajectories shape young people’s professional visions [15].

The purpose of this study is to identify and conceptualize mechanisms for strengthening motivation and retention among dual-education students in Uzbekistan’s MICE sector by developing a system of regular communication with parents on practice and employment issues as a form of social support for learning. The scientific novelty of the work lies in shifting the focus from the institutional dyad “college-enterprise” to an expanded triad “educational organization-employer-family”, which enables the description of social determinants of dual education persistence and supports the proposal of a measurable monitoring framework.

Materials and methods

The study is conducted as an analytical review complemented by comparative analysis and the development of an applied implementation scheme. The empirical basis comprises three groups of secondary materials: legal and regulatory acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan on dual education and workforce training; publications and materials describing the development of MICE and hospitality; and international studies on staff turnover and the role of family support in educational and career transitions.

The analytical procedure included three steps. First, a content analysis of regulatory documents was conducted to identify the distribution of roles among participants in dual education and requirements for organizing workplace practice. Second, key parameters of dual education in Uzbekistan and Germany were compared as a reference system, allowing identification of institutional vulnerabilities at the early stage of reform [16]. Third, based on a synthesis of international findings on family support and parental engagement programs, the logic of an applied intervention was developed, and a set of measurable indicators was specified in advance to assess completion of the dual period, early retention, and behavioral mechanisms through which program effects may be realized.

To ensure verifiability of conclusions, core concepts were translated into measurable indicators, and data sources were selected with attention to feasibility at the level of an educational organization and a partner company. The resulting indicator scheme and recording methods are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Indicators and data sources

Indicator	Operationalization	Data source
Dual-education persistence	Completion of the dual period, absence of early contract termination	Administrative data of educational organizations and partner companies
Early retention in the profession	Duration of employment after graduation (6 and 12 months)	HR reports of partner companies
Family support	Parents’ awareness of the profession, frequency of supportive communication	Surveys of parents and students, knowledge testing
Student career confidence	Self-assessment and intention to continue a career in mice	Student questionnaires
Mentoring quality	Presence of a mentor, regularity of feedback, structure of practice	Surveys of students and mentors, enterprise regulatory documents

Table 1 establishes an evaluation logic in which ultimate outcomes, completion of the dual period and retention after graduation, are linked to intermediate mechanisms. These mechanisms include family awareness, supportive communication, and student career confidence, as well as mentoring quality as a key condition influencing practice persistence. This linkage makes it possible to interpret piloting results not only as the presence or absence of an effect but as an explainable change dependent on specific factors of practice organization and social support.

Results

The analysis confirms that the development of MICE in Uzbekistan is accompanied by expanding infrastructure and increasing service quality requirements, which strengthens demand for specialists able to work within a project-based logic and under high communication and coordination loads [1]. The expansion of the hotel base and investment activity in hospitality further increase workforce demand and heighten concerns regarding training quality [2].

Dual education is institutionally supported and considered a mechanism of practice-oriented training in which a substantial share of time is transferred to the workplace and the mentor role is normatively defined [4]. However, assessing system persistence requires not only expansion of coverage but also the ability of learners to complete the dual period and become established in the profession. Therefore, the study uses comparison with German practice as a reference point to clarify which parameters are particularly vulnerable at the early stage of implementation and which compensatory solutions can be applied without restructuring the regulatory model [16]. This comparison is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. comparison of selected parameters of dual education in Uzbekistan and Germany

Parameter	Uzbekistan	Germany	Interpretation for this study
Institutionalization start	2021/2022 academic year	Historically stable system (since the 1970s)	The Uzbek model is in an adaptation and learning phase
Scale of participation	Growing numbers of students and partner organizations	High share of youth involved	Coverage expansion should be accompanied by strengthened results monitoring
Completion of training	No open, comparable completion indicators	High completion rates	Data gaps make measurement of completion and retention a

Parameter	Uzbekistan	Germany	Interpretation for this study
			priority
Mentor role	Formally defined but heterogeneous in quality	Stable institutional role of the mentor	Mentoring quality is a key outcome determinant
Family inclusion	Not systematically formalized, identified as a gap	Typically not institutionalized, but VET status is higher	The family component can serve as a compensatory mechanism at an early reform stage

Table 2 indicates that, in the Uzbek context, two issues are particularly sensitive: the lack of comparable data on dual-education completion and early retention, and the heterogeneity of mentoring practices despite the formal designation of this role. Under such conditions, scaling dual education does not guarantee stable professional trajectories, and a key task becomes the parallel construction of outcome measurement and risk reduction for premature withdrawal from training.

Sectoral risk of early exit is reinforced by the combination of three factors. First, a gap persists between employer expectations and graduates’ actual preparation, as reflected in the sector skills assessment [8]. Second, hospitality is characterized by high turnover and associated economic losses documented in international estimates [10-11]. Third, the youth-dominated labor market structure increases sensitivity to the quality of first employment experience and the stability of professional choice [9]. Together, these factors imply that persistence in a dual pathway depends not only on practice organization but also on the support a student receives during adaptation to real work regimes.

To move from the general claim of family significance to an applied design, the study identifies typical family-level barriers that affect motivation, expectations, and persistence of decisions to continue training and work. The literature shows that parental support is especially important for educational persistence and strengthening career confidence, and that targeted family engagement programs can reduce anxiety and increase training module completion [13-14]. In addition, family background and parental educational capital are linked to the formation of young people’s professional orientations [15]. A typology of barriers and directions of the parental engagement program is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. family-level motivational barriers and directions of the parental engagement program

Barriers at the family level	How they manifest	Direction of the parental engagement program	Expected effect (change logic)
Underestimation of vocational education	Preference for higher education pathways detached from labor market demand	Clarification of career trajectories and occupational status, demonstration of successful cases	Increased legitimacy of vocational choice within the family
Limited understanding of MICE work regimes	Seasonal peak loads, project-based work, unstable schedules	Training in financial and family planning under project employment, review of typical contracts	Reduced expectation conflict, stronger support during adaptation

Barriers at the family level	How they manifest	Direction of the parental engagement program	Expected effect (change logic)
Misguided expectations of “quick results”	Frustration due to low entry-level positions and high client demands	Explanation of professional growth model and the role of practice and mentoring	Realistic expectations, reduced propensity to leave the profession
Deficit of emotional support	Devaluation of difficulties, low empathy toward workload	Modules on stress and burnout, tools for supportive communication	Reduced burnout risk and early exit
Limited social capital	Lack of success models and professional networks	Engagement of alumni and hr as mentors for families, networking meetings	Increased career confidence and broader family information field

Table 3 supports treating the family as a manageable element of the social context of dual education that influences pathway persistence through three practical mechanisms.

- The first mechanism relates to legitimizing vocational choice within the family, so that the student’s decision is perceived as socially acceptable and promising.
- The second mechanism concerns aligning expectations regarding work regimes and the pace of career growth, reducing the likelihood of early-stage disappointment.
- The third mechanism involves supportive communication during high-load periods, when the risks of emotional burnout and withdrawal are highest.

Given these mechanisms, the study proposes a format of parent career-navigation sessions as regular but organizationally simple events tied to key transitions in the dual pathway: the start of practice, the first outcomes, and entry into the first job. Substantively, the program integrates three components: information about the labor market and career routes in MICE; alignment of expectations regarding professional behavior and discipline requirements; and tools to support students under stress and intense workload. This format differs fundamentally from one-off informational meetings because it creates a sustainable communication channel among the educational organization, employer, and family, reducing information gaps and improving expectation alignment.

Since the study is review-analytical and does not claim empirically measured effects for Uzbekistan, a key result is the piloting scheme in which the program is pre-linked to measurable indicators. The monitoring system for the pilot is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. monitoring system for evaluating the parental engagement program for piloting

Category	Indicator	Unit	Observation period	Source and method
Completion of the dual period	Share of students completing the dual period without discontinuation	%	End of semester/year	Administrative data of institutions and companies
Early	Share of graduates remaining	%	6 and 12	HR reports, graduate

Category	Indicator	Unit	Observation period	Source and method
retention	employed in mice after 6 and 12 months		months post-graduation	tracking
Mentoring quality	Regularity of mentor feedback and presence of a practice plan	Score/checkbox list	Monthly	Surveys of students and mentors, company regulations
Family awareness	Level of knowledge of key facts about the profession and labor market	Test score	Before and after modules	Parent testing, short questionnaires
Family support	Frequency of supportive conversations about work and study	Times/week	Monthly	Surveys of students and parents
Career confidence	Self-assessed stability of professional choice	Scale score	Before and after the program	Student questionnaires
Economic effects	Estimated costs of staff replacement and adaptation time	Monetary and time indicators	Annually	Company finance and HR data, calculations based on source approaches

The monitoring system in Table 4 supports an “process-to-outcome” evaluation logic. It captures ultimate outcomes, completion and early retention, as well as intermediate changes in family awareness, supportive communication, and student career confidence. This is important for interpreting pilot results because it enables explaining effects through concrete mechanisms rather than merely stating their presence or absence. Simultaneously, incorporating mentoring quality and the economic parameters of turnover provides an operational management framework for employers by linking social support to practical costs of recruitment and staff adaptation.

Discussion

The proposed parental engagement program is discussed as an organizationally feasible measure that complements dual education at the point where a gap most often arises between educational trajectories and actual work regimes. Importantly, the family component does not replace production and educational quality mechanisms but increases the likelihood of completing the dual period by reducing expectation conflicts and strengthening motivational stability during adaptation. This framing is consistent with research findings that describe parental support as a resource for educational persistence and career confidence, and that attribute the effects of targeted family engagement programs to changes in everyday communication and household behavior [13-14].

From a practical perspective, the program can be integrated into the existing regulatory architecture of dual education without altering the distribution of time between classroom learning and workplace practice established by Resolution No. 163 [4]. The most rational approach is piloting within partner MICE organizations with subsequent evaluation using the indicator system to build a national evidence base and determine which components contribute most under varying practice conditions. At the same time, expected effects will depend on two conditions: mentoring quality and transparency of professional growth pathways within the

enterprise. If these conditions are not met, the risk of disappointment and early exit may persist even under strong family support because students face uncertainty of requirements and lack a clear prospect.

Study limitations are associated with reliance on secondary sources and the lack of open data on dual-education completion and retention in Uzbekistan’s MICE segment. Accordingly, the article does not claim quantitative effects as nationally proven but proposes a measurable piloting scheme that enables accumulation of comparable results and supports a transition from a conceptual solution to evidence-based conclusions in the national context. An additional limitation concerns differences between institutional conditions of dual education in Uzbekistan and Germany, implying that transfer is possible only at the level of principles and quality management logic rather than direct copying of institutions [16].

Conclusion

The development of MICE in Uzbekistan is accompanied by rising demand for qualified personnel, while the institutionalization of dual education creates a foundation for practice-oriented training. At the same time, sectoral risks of turnover and skill mismatch persist, and the social component related to family attitudes remains an underutilized resource. The proposed parental engagement program expands the architecture of dual education through regular work with students’ families and establishes a manageable channel for aligning expectations among the student, employer, and household. To support a transition from concept to evidence-based policy, a monitoring system is proposed that enables pilot projects and quantitative assessment of program impacts on dual-period completion and early retention in the profession.

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